

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF PSYCHOLINGUISTIC METHODS IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract. English as a specific subject includes the mastery of a particular speaking activity, its linguistic material, as well as the actions and operations associated with it. The process of teaching English is provided by speaking skills and the ability to understand, speak, read and write in the language. These skills are primarily intended to practice English. Linguistic tools are the basis of language: phonetic, lexical, grammatical; their growth is based on knowledge in the field of language aspects (phonetics, vocabulary, grammar). Consequently, it is advisable to include data and skills in the curriculum created on the tools and language skills providing in the teaching of foreign language for students. Practical language skills include the provision of mixed-ability levels of linguistic symbols (exercises consisting of phrases) will also be the scaffolding issue for the student's learning of a foreign language. Therefore, various forms related to language and systems of their use are also included in the teaching content.

Keywords: Psycholinguistics, field requirement, field authenticity, English speech perception, teaching CLT, cognitive (priority / flexibility) management, a compulsive task.

Аннотация. Английский язык как специфический предмет включает в себя владение определенной речевой деятельностью, ее языковым материалом, а также связанными с ней действиями и операциями. Процесс обучения английскому языку обеспечивается навыками разговорной речи и умением понимать, говорить, читать и писать на языке. Эти навыки в первую очередь предназначены для практики английского языка. Основу языка составляют лингвистические средства: фонетические, лексические и грамматические; их рост основан на знаниях в области языковых аспектов (фонетики, лексики, грамматики). Следовательно, целесообразно включать в учебную программу данные и навыки, созданные на основе средств и языковых навыков, предусмотренных при обучении студентов иностранным языкам. Практические языковые навыки, включающие в себя обеспечение смешанного уровня владения языковыми символами (упражнения, состоящие из фраз), также будут опорным вопросом для изучения студентом иностранного языка. Поэтому в содержание обучения также включены различные формы, связанные с языком и системами его использования.

Ключевые слова: Психолингвистика, требования, независимость, восприятие английской речи, обучение CLT, когнитивное (приоритет/гибкость) управление, компульсивное задание.

Annotatsiya. Ingliz tili fan sifatida muayyan nutqiy faoliyatni, uning lingvistik materialini, shuningdek, u bilan bog'liq harakatlar va operatsiyalarni o'zlashtirishni o'z ichiga oladi. Ingliz tilini o'qitish jarayoni nutq qobiliyatlari va tilda tushunish, gapirish, o'qish va yozish qobiliyati bilan ta'minlanadi. Bu ko'nikmalar birinchi navbatda ingliz tilini mashq qilish uchun mo'ljallangan. Tilning asosini lingvistik vositalar tashkil etadi: fonetik, leksik va grammatik; ularning o'sishi til aspektlari (fonetika, lug'at, grammatika) sohasidagi bilimlarga asoslanadi. Binobarin, talabalarga chet tillarini o'rgatishda ko'zda tutilgan vositalar va til ko'nikmalari bo'yicha tuzilgan o'quv rejasiga ma'lumotlar va ko'nikmalarni kiritish maqsadga muvofiqdir. Amaliy til ko'nikmalari lingvistik belgilarning aralash qobiliyatlarini (iboralardan iborat mashqlar) ta'minlashni o'z ichiga oladi, shuningdek, talabaning chet tilini o'rganishi uchun asos

bo'ladi. Shuning uchun tilga oid turli shakllar va ulardan foydalanish tizimlari ham o'qitish mazmuniga kiritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: *Psixolingvistika, soha talabi, haqqoniylik, ingliz nutqini idrok etish, CLTni o'qitish, kognitiv (ustuvorlik / moslashuvchanlik) boshqaruvi, majburiy vazifa.*

The required need for English as a foreign language in the question of what methods teachers should choose, and the matter of teaching children of all ages is always relevant. It is very substantial to choose work methods reliant on the age characteristics of the child and his level of knowledge. When choosing exercises, it is also imperative to be aware of the psychological exercises in which the process of English speech perception and reproduction takes place. The problem of defined laws is solved by the science of psycholinguistics. This subject will help answer two questions related to foreign language teaching. First, it is clear that for autonomy of speech, the student must master lexical-grammatical and phonetic material and acquire remarkable communication skills. That is, not only theoretical preparation, but also activities aimed at evolving mechanisms of speech communication are necessary. In this case, methods such as integrated skills (writing, speaking, reading and listening) help. Through reading and listening, the learner advances the skills of distinguishing language material and studies to quickly form ideas in English while writing and speaking. Second, psycholinguistics allows students to choose an individual approach based on the child's cognitive style. Psycholinguistics identifies the following key features of core skills that affect the way, speed, and quality of learning new material.

1. Field requirement / field authenticity.

A field requirement is characterized by a high tendency for communication, depending on the group. In this case, it is worthwhile to involve the students in group work exercises so that he or she can gain the trust of the group and team building if he or she succeeds and be supported whether he or she fails.

Mostly, English textbooks provide an introductory exercise in which students cooperate with the group to practice their foreign language skills. This task is best suited for learners with a character-dependent field can be seen as scaffolding issue.

Field authenticity is characterized by high personal autonomy, low level of interest in other people, isolation. For this type of learner, it is recommended to give assignments for self-study work.

For instance, it can be a duty to effort independently with a textbook: rewrite words, find descriptions of things in a textbook, fill in gaps, and so on.

2. Cognitive (priority / flexibility) management

A learner with high cognitive control finds it difficult to concentrate because of the persistent interruptions in the classroom. For instance, noise or other interruptions can confuse a child from physical skills and specifically from basic activities. In students with the flexibility of cognitive regulator, information is straightforwardly adjusted, regardless of the effects on sensory perception. Concentration training tasks will be cooperative for a teen-ager with severe cognitive control. For instance, in a workout in searching for a supplementary section that is external to the row, the student develops the following skills:

- | | |
|--------------------------------|------------------------|
| 1. Say the introductory speech | a. Once upon a time... |
| 2. Repeat the tongue twister | b. Good morning, ... |
| 3. Make a story | c. I live in... |

4. Describe-what is success?
canner can cans.

d. How many cans, can a canner can if he is a

Task 3. Exercise: matching words with appropriate pair.

It is recommended to analyze and compare multiple data with a cognitive method through reasoning and to give tasks that need a final answer. An example of such an assignment is listening, in which a student has to associate numerous answer options based on the text he or she has listened to in the form of a test. Comparing foreign words with their structures or characteristics will also be a prompt task to indicate the right possibility from the list of given words. 4. Reflection should be given to the way material is supposed: working through auditory, visual, or kinesthetic skills. For the reason that it is determining the method of perception for each student can be challenging for the teacher, it is recommended that various types of information be presented and reinforced. It is optional to use tables, and diagrams, accompanied by their explanations, and then inspire students to repeat what they have heard or seen before. Listening exercises or listening comprehension are suggested. Visual skills training includes reading or writing text, reviewing a picture, or redrawing it. It is best to use workouts that focus on multiple skills at the same time. This can be done by selecting pictures that match each other, or by choosing a picture that matches the words. In teaching English, it is necessary to develop four main types of talking activities that are distinguished in psycholinguistics: listening (listening), speaking, reading, and writing. Oral speech involves speaking and listening, and writing includes reading and writing. To secondary types of speech action - paraphrase. Based on this, it is necessary to choose exercises to develop each type of speech activity. This can be done not only through textbook exercises but also through play activities. For learners to master a new language, it is necessary to gradually increase the creative level of the speaker. However, it is necessary to rely on the level of knowledge of the learner. There are three levels of a speaker: The first level of reproduction: the person repeats the words or sentences they hear. At this stage, preparation is usually made to read or listen to the text in English. The teacher should give about ten new words and ask them to write them in the dictionary, and then repeat them aloud. The second level is reproductive and effective: ready-made blocks (words or phrases) should be used to convey the idea. At this point, the exercises are suitable for composing sentences from ready words or phrases. The third level is productive: it is regarded as the speaker's ability to form sentences independently and to construct a sentence creatively. Despite the effectiveness of out-of-date exercises, mingling them with games is more beneficial. As the leading activity can be changed according to the level, and shifts from play to learning, the play form accelerates and improves the process of mastering the material. However, the game is conveyed by positive emotions and does not resist, which helps to consolidate more information not only in the short-term but also in long-term memory.

One of the well-known researchers in game psychology is Elkonin Daniil Borisovich, who made significant contributions to both pedagogy and psychology. In his manuscript *Game Psychology*, Elkonin D.B. The practice of turning a compulsive task into a play task allows resistance to be removed, resulting in children enjoying doing what they need to do while unindustrialized thinking and imagination.

In learning English, especially with teenagers, the basic methods can be used to combine new information and check the level of mastery.

While learning and introducing about specific topics, the teacher may invite the learners to bring realia to class or the staff which can be interesting to show and describe. The course layout helps reduce anxiety, stimulates interest in learning and practicing a new language, and covers all

methods of learning new information. The staff also undoubtedly evokes positive emotions, which helps to better remember new information and establish a friendly, trusting relationship with the teacher, which is especially important in team work. In teaching a foreign language to students, especially in different situations of oral communication, it is appropriate to take into consideration the fact that all the treasure of the world is manifested as the main source of knowledge. It can be used as a means of language learning and communication, and the learner listens, speaks, reads, and writes. Oral and written speech through language means (sounds, letters), according to the conditions (interaction of communication and communicative) - the role of verbal dialogue, spoken monologue and written monologues is unique. Students are given information by productive skills as listening and reading; the information given can be transmitted orally or in writing in the analysis. Listening and speaking are two aspects of oral communication, which, undeniably, are explained by the commonality of linguistic and oral material, non-linguistic means. Types of speech activities can be included in this or that learning activity autonomously. This means that reading is used to expand and deepen professional knowledge, and the material obtained in this way can further excite nonverbal and speech movements.

In conclusion, it should be noted that psycholinguistics has made a significant contribution to the process of teaching a foreign language, especially in terms of teaching methods in the lower grades. This science allows us to determine what activities are focused on and in what ways it should be done, based on the flow of a person's speech and cognitive processes. It should be noted the high effectiveness of exercises conducted in the form of games, Furthermore, the effectiveness of this work is related to the removal of internal barriers of students, the emergence of confident emotions, which increases the interest in learning the language, the level of memorization of new information and the teacher and the reader in general, the level of confidence in the detection process growths.

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